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Research Article

**ENDOSCOPIC FINDINGS OF GASTROESOPHAGEAL
JUNCTION IN INDIVIDUALS WITH CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS
OF GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE****Dr. Mansoor Asad Kalwar¹, Dr. Riaz Hussain Awan^{2*}, Dr. Seema Nayab³,
Dr. Khadim Hussain Awan⁴, Dr. Faqir Muhammad Awan⁵**¹ Resident, Department of Gastroenterology, Liaquat National Hospital, Karachi² Assistant Professor, Department of Gastroenterology, LUMHS, Jamshoro³ Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, LUMHS, Jamshoro⁴ Resident, Department of Urology Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore⁵ Resident Cardiology Shaikh Zaid Hospital, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: To evaluate the frequency of various endoscopic findings of gastroesophageal junction in individuals with clinical diagnosis of gastroesophageal reflux disease.

Patients and methods: This study was conducted as cross sectional study of six months at Liaquat National Hospital Karachi. All individuals 18-60 years, either gender had clinical diagnosis of GERD \geq 8 weeks duration were enrolled and recruited. All the subjects underwent endoscopic examination while the findings were recorded on proforma and analyzed in SPSS.

Results: The overall mean \pm SD for age, duration of symptoms and weight was 43.07 \pm 18.94 years, 11.44 \pm 2.02 months and 70.91 \pm 14.70 kg while the male and female proportions were detected as 60 (43.20%) and 79 (56.80%). The reflux oesophagitis was identified in 14 (10.10%), cloumnar lined oesophagus 34 (24.50%) and hiatus hernia 19 (13.70%) individuals on endoscopy.

Conclusion: Reflux oesophagitis 14 (10.10%), cloumnar lined oesophagus 34 (24.50%) and hiatus hernia 19 (13.70%) at gastroesophageal junction in clinical diagnosis of gastroesophageal reflux disease population.

Keywords: Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease, Hiatus Hernia and Reflux oesophagitis.

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INTRODUCTION:

Gastro esophageal reflux disease is major gastrointestinal disorder reported during outpatient clinics visits [1-3]. There is contradiction between correspondence of symptoms and endoscopic findings of the GERD [4,5]. The former study explored individuals through random sampling and reported the prevalence as 1.6% and 15.5% for Barrett's esophagus and esophagitis and one third of esophagitis reported having reflux symptoms [6]. The prevalence of Reflux esophagitis (RE) ranges from 3% to 16%; in an study from Asia the prevalence of HH was proved to be 14.3% [7-10]. In former studies the relationship among GERD and several demographic and behavioral elements as age, educational level, gender and socioeconomic status has been proved [11,12]. The inconsistencies in GERD prevalence and possible associated risk factors however may be the result due to geographical variations, socioeconomic class, life habits in different countries and ethnic group (like alcohol intake, patterns of sleep), methodological differences related to definition and exploration of GERD symptoms [12]. In another study in Asia the prevalence of columnar lined esophagus was 23.3% whereas of CLE the documented intestinal metaplasia was 14.1% [13].

Rationale of this study was; although GERD is traditionally considered a etiological factor of Barrett's esophagus which is a potential pre-malignant condition, no local study specifically addressing the complications of GERD has been observed. The incidence of this complication and various other endoscopic findings around GE junction is unknown locally. A better exploration of GERD leads to early detection of those individuals who are at risk of several complication and various other endoscopic findings around GE junction that are associated with GERD, These patients may therefore benefit from prophylactic measures aimed at relieving the symptoms associated with GERD. The observations of this study considered as valid as the population recruited has different economic class, ethnic groups, and lifestyles visiting at tertiary care hospital of Karachi Pakistan.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The 06 months (June 14, 2013 to December 13, 2013) cross sectional study was conducted at Liaquat National Hospital Karachi. Total at least n=139 study subjects will be included in this study. The sample size was calculated using WHO software for sample size determination using $P=10\%$ $d=5\%$ and 95% confidence interval.

Inclusion criteria

1. Patients 18-60 years of age
2. Symptoms of GERD for ≥ 8 weeks duration.
3. Either gender.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with peptic ulcer, dysphagia, hematemesis, melena or already on non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), anti-platelet agents, proton pump inhibitors (PPI),

1. Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease: Defined as the existence of regurgitation of acid or burning of heart, or both. Heartburn (burning pain or discomfort behind the breast bone in chest) whereas the acid regurgitation (sour tasting or bitter fluid coming in mouth or throat). If two or more than two "yes" in "Richter Acid Scale" questionnaire, it will indicate the presence of Gastro esophageal reflux. (Details of Richter Acid Scale questionnaire mentioned in Annex-I)
2. Endoscopic Findings
 - a) Reflux esophagitis (10.5%) [5].
 - b) Hiatus hernia (14.3%)⁶.
 - c) Columnar lined Esophagus (23.3%) [13].

All the relevant patients were recruited by taking informed consent and underwent for endoscopic examination. The intervention was done by single consultant having ≥ 10 years clinical experience in upper gastrointestinal endoscopies or GI fellows having at least 18 months experience in upper gastrointestinal endoscopy under direct supervision of the above mentioned consultant. Endoscopic findings (as specified previously) was recorded on a preformed proforma. Statistical package of social science (SPSS) version 17.0 was used to evaluate the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for quantitative while the frequencies and percentages was computed for qualitative variables. The ratio (M: F) was computed to present gender, while the smoking and alcohol addiction and the presence or absence of other co-morbidities like diabetes, Hypertension was stratified to control the confounders, applying chi-Square test $p \leq 0.05$ as significant.

RESULTS:

The overall mean \pm SD for age, duration of symptoms and weight was 43.07 ± 18.94 years, 11.44 ± 2.02 months and 70.91 ± 14.70 kg. Most of the patients 82 (59%) were presented in >35 years of age.

Most of the patients 84 (60.40%) were presented with >65Kg weight.

Most of the patients 79 (56.80%) were presented with ≤11 months duration of symptoms.

There were 60 (43.20%) male and 79 (56.80%) females.

There were 58 (41.70%) smokers, 16 (11.50%) alcohol addicted, 79 (56.80%) diabetic, 70 (50.40%) hypertensive patients.

Endoscopic observations as reflux oesophagitis in 14 (10.10%), cloumnar lined oesophagus 34 (24.50%) and hiatus hernia 19 (13.70%) patients.

The results are presented in Table 1-4 and Figure 1-6

TABLE 1:AGE OF THE PATIENTS n=139

Mean ±SD	Minimum	Maximum
43.07 ±18.94	18	60

TABLE 2: COMPARISON OF REFLUX OESOPHAGITIS WITH DIFFERENT VARIABLES

n=139

Variables		Reflux Oesophagitis		Total	p-value
		Yes	No		
Age	≤35	2 (3.5)	55 (96.5)	57 (100)	0.032
	>35	12 (14.6)	70 (85.4)	82 (100)	
Weight	≤65	11 (20)	44 (80)	55 (100)	0.002
	>65	3 (3.6)	81 (96.4)	84 (100)	
Duration of symptoms	≤11	5 (6.3)	74 (93.7)	79 (100)	0.092
	>11	9 (15)	51 (85)	60 (100)	
Gender	Male	9 (15)	51 (85)	60 (100)	0.092
	Female	5 (6.3)	74 (93.7)	79 (100)	
Smoking Status	Yes	10 (17.2)	48 (82.8)	58 (100)	0.017
	No	4 (4.9)	77 (95.1)	81 (100)	
Alcohol Addiction	Yes	7 (43.8)	9 (56.3)	16 (100)	0.001
	No	7 (5.7)	116 (94.3)	123 (100)	
Diabetes	Yes	14 (17.7)	65 (82.3)	79 (100)	0.001
	No	0 (0)	60 (100)	60 (100)	
HTN	Yes	14 (20)	56 (80)	70 (100)	0.001
	No	0 (0)	69 (100)	69 (100)	

TABLE 3
COMPARISION OF HIATUS HERNIA WITH DIFFERENT VARIABLES

n=139

Variables		Hiatus Hernia		Total	p-value
		Yes	No		
Age	≤35	2 (3.5)	55 (96.5)	57 (100)	0.004
	>35	17 (20.7)	65 (79.3)	82 (100)	
Weight	≤65	11 (20)	44 (80)	55 (100)	0.079
	>65	8 (9.5)	76 (90.5)	84 (100)	
Duration of symptoms	≤11	7 (8.9)	72 (91.1)	79 (100)	0.058
	>11	12 (20)	48 (80)	60 (100)	
Gender	Male	9 (15)	51 (85)	60 (100)	0.691
	Female	10 (12.7)	69 (87.3)	79 (100)	
Smoking Status	Yes	15 (25.9)	43 (74.1)	58 (100)	0.001
	No	4 (4.9)	77 (95.1)	81 (100)	
Alcohol Addiction	Yes	7 (43.8)	9 (56.3)	16 (100)	0.001
	No	12 (9.8)	111 (90.2)	123 (100)	
Diabetes	Yes	17 (21.5)	62 (78.5)	79 (100)	0.002
	No	2 (3.3)	58 (96.7)	60 (100)	
HTN	Yes	19 (27.1)	51 (72.9)	70 (100)	0.001
	No	0 (0)	69 (100)	69 (100)	

TABLE 4

COMPARISON OF COLUMNAR LINED OESOPHAGUS WITH DIFFERENT VARIABLES

n=139

Variables		Columnar Lined Oesophagus		Total	p-value
		Yes	No		
Age	≤35	14 (24.6)	43 (75.4)	57 (100)	0.982
	>35	20 (24.4)	62 (75.6)	82 (100)	
Weight	≤65	15 (27.3)	40 (72.7)	55 (100)	0.533
	>65	19 (22.6)	65 (77.4)	84 (100)	
Duration of symptoms	≤11	17 (21.5)	62 (78.5)	79 (100)	0.355
	>11	17 (28.3)	43 (71.7)	60 (100)	
Gender	Male	9 (15)	51 (85)	60 (100)	0.024
	Female	25 (31.6)	54 (68.4)	79 (100)	
Smoking Status	Yes	30 (51.7)	28 (48.3)	58 (100)	0.001
	No	4 (4.9)	77 (95.1)	81 (100)	
Alcohol Addiction	Yes	7 (43.8)	9 (56.3)	16 (100)	0.056
	No	27 (22)	96 (78)	123 (100)	
Diabetes	Yes	17 (21.5)	62 (78.5)	79 (100)	0.355
	No	17 (28.3)	43 (71.7)	60 (100)	
HTN	Yes	22 (31.4)	48 (68.6)	70 (100)	0.054
	No	12 (17.4)	57 (82.6)	69 (100)	

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of GERD in the Western world was estimated to be 10% to 20% and there is contradiction between correspondence of symptoms and endoscopic features of the GERD.^{14, 15} In this study, reflux oesophagitis was found in 14 (10.10%), cloumnar lined oesophagus 34 (24.50%) patients and hiatus hernia 19 (13.70%). Somewhat similar results were observed formerly as Barrett's esophagus 1.6%, esophagitis 15.5% and 40% of Barrett's esophagus subjects and one third of esophagitis reported having reflux symptoms.⁹ It has been observed formerly that reflux esophagitis ranges from 3% to 16%^{9,11} while Asian prevalence for H.H was reported as 14.3%.⁶ In previous studies the relationship among GERD & several behavioral and demographic factors as age, educational level, gender and socioeconomic status has been observed.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ The inconsistencies in GERD prevalence and possible associated risk factors however may be due to geographical variations, socioeconomic class, life habits in different countries and ethnic group (like alcohol intake, patterns of sleep) related to the definition and exploration of GERD symptoms.^{20,21} In former literature the endoscopic findings of GERD patients reported as reflux oesophagitis & distal esophagus endoscopic erythema, hiatus hernia and cloumnar lined oesophagus in various international studies.²²⁻²⁵ The findings of current series are also consistent with the former literature related to GERD in accordance to smoking, hypertension, alcohol and diabetes mellitus.²⁶⁻²⁸

CONCLUSION:

Endoscopic observations revealed reflux oesophagitis, hiatus hernia and cloumnar lined oesophagus at gastroesophageal junction in individuals with gastroesophageal reflux disease.

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